

Spectrophotometric Studies on Metal Chelates. Part III. Gallium-salicylic Acid Complex

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The colorless complex, formed by the reaction between Ga^{3+} and salicylic acid, has been studied spectrophotometrically. The molecular composition has been determined by Job's method of continued variation. The dissociation constants at pH 3.0 and 3.5 at different ionic strengths have also been determined. The thermodynamic quantities, ΔH and ΔS , have been calculated from the temperature coefficient of the instability constant.

In course of our investigations on complexes formed by hydroxy-acids and their derivatives with various bivalent and trivalent metal ions like Be^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Ga^{3+} etc., the system, gallium-salicylic acid, has been studied by ultraviolet spectrophotometry. The molecular composition of the complex has been determined and the instability constants at different pH's, ionic strengths, and temperatures have been evaluated. From the temperature coefficient of the instability constant, the thermodynamic quantities, ΔH and ΔS , for the complex-formation reaction has been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Gallium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving 99.9% pure gallium oxide (John Mathey) in HCl, precipitating the hydroxide by addition of alkali, washing the precipitate, and subsequently dissolving it in perchloric acid. The gallium content of the stock solution was estimated by precipitating and weighing as oxinate.

E. Merck (G.R.) salicylic acid was dissolved in double distilled water to prepare the stock solution. It was estimated by titrating against alkali, standardised against potassium biphthalate ((G.R.). All other chemicals were of pure grade. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Absorption measurements were done in a Hilger-Watt "Uvispek" spectrophotometer (Model H 700-303). Matched quartz cells with 1 cm path length were used. pH measurements were done with a Marconi pH-meter (Model TF 511D). Other experimental details were the same as described in our earlier communications¹.

DISCUSSION

Gallium perchlorate is transparent between 280 m μ and 350 m μ . Salicylic acid has an absorption maximum around 296 m μ . Addition of gallium perchlorate to this causes the

1. *This Journal*, 1959, 36, 473; 1960, 37, 557; 1961, 38, 19.

shift in the absorption maximum to higher wave lengths, suggesting complex formation. As has been observed in other systems¹, the extent of shift increases with increase of pH; the shift is appreciable above pH 2.5 and is maximum around pH 3.5. Investigation above pH 4.0 could not be carried out because of precipitation of gallium, presumably as hydroxide.

Composition of the Complex.—Job's method² of continued variation was used to determine the molecular composition of the complex. Absorbances of two sets of solutions at pH 3.5 containing different proportions of gallium and salicylic acid, keeping the total molalities constant at 3.0×10^{-4} and 4.0×10^{-4} , were measured at different wave lengths. In Fig. 1 are reproduced the curves for the total molarity of 3.0×10^{-4} obtained on plotting $\bar{D}$'s against the composition ratios at wave lengths 290 m μ , 310 m μ , and 320 m μ . Those for total molarity of 4×10^{-4} were similar. The positions of maxima and minima in the curves suggest that only one complex, corresponding to the ratio of the metal and ligand in the proportion of 1:1, exists in the solution at pH 3.5. At lower pH's the probability of any other complex (1:2 or 1:3) existing in solution is therefore very little.

$$\frac{[\text{Ga}^{3+}]}{[\text{Ga}^{3+}] + [\text{sal. acid}]}$$
 FIG. 1
 Curves I-III refer to 290, 310 and 320 m μ respectively.

$$1/T \rightarrow$$
 FIG. 2

Extinction Coefficient.—Extinction coefficients of the complex and the ligand at wave length 310 m μ were determined in the same way as in our earlier communications¹ at pH's 3.0 and 3.5. The average values of the extinction coefficients of the complex at 310 m μ are (3695 ± 6) and (4073 ± 3) at pH 3.5 and 3.0 respectively. The same for salicylic acid at the above pH's have been found to be (2340 ± 8) and (2599 ± 4) respectively.

Instability Constant.—Instability constant of the complex

$$K_{in} = \frac{\{[Ga^{3+}]_{total} - [Complex]\} \{[Sal]_{total} - [Complex]\}}{[Complex]}$$

has been calculated as in our earlier communications at different pH's and ionic strengths. At pH 3.5 the values are $(2.89 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-3}$, $(5.42 \pm 0.18) \times 10^{-3}$, $(7.45 \pm 0.25) \times 10^{-3}$, and $(1.06 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-4}$ corresponding to ionic strengths 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2 respectively at the room temperature which varied $(30 \pm 1^\circ)$ during the course of measurements.

At pH 3.0, the instability constants have been determined at ionic strengths 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2. The average values are $(2.02 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-4}$, $(2.62 \pm 0.09) \times 10^{-4}$, and $(3.54 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-4}$ respectively. The measurements were done at temperatures varying between 28° and 29° . As expected, in both the cases the instability constant increased with the increase of ionic strength.

TABLE I

Wave length = 310 m μ . Cell width = 1 cm.

Ionic strength.	No. of readings taken with varying conc. of the reactants.	Av. value of instability const.
A. pH = 3.5. Temp. = $31.^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.		
0.02	8	$(2.89 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-3}$
0.05	9	$(5.42 \pm 0.18) \times 10^{-3}$
0.10	8	$(7.45 \pm 0.25) \times 10^{-3}$
0.20	6	$(1.06 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-4}$
B. pH = 3.0. Temp. = $28.5^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.		
0.05	10	$(2.02 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-4}$
0.10	9	$(2.62 \pm 0.09) \times 10^{-4}$
0.20	9	$(3.54 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-4}$

A comparison of the instability constants at the corresponding ionic strengths at pH 3.5 and 3.0 shows that these are clearly different. Incorporation of H^+ ion concentration at its first power in the denominator provides values of ' K_d ' which are recorded in Table II. For comparison, the values of the constants at pH 3.0 for 31° have been obtained by interpolation from the constants at 20° , 28.5° , and 40° .

TABLE II

pH.	K_d at $\mu = 0.05$.	K_d at $\mu = 0.1$.	K_d at $\mu = 0.2$.
3.5	(0.172 ± 0.006)	(0.236 ± 0.008)	(0.337 ± 0.013)
3.0	(0.188 ± 0.007)	(0.247 ± 0.009)	(0.334 ± 0.011)

The agreement between the values is fairly good, considering experimental limitations. The system is definitely pH-dependant and since the incorporation of the H^+ ion concentra-

tion in the manner, indicated above, explains the results, the equilibrium should be represented according to the scheme:

where HR^- stands for

Entropy and Enthalpy Changes.—The instability constants at $p\text{H}$ 3.0 and at ionic strength 0.05 were determined at 20° and 40°, besides the determination at the room temperature (28.5°). The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

$p\text{H} = 3.0.$ Wave length = 310 $m\mu.$ Cell width = 1 cm. $\mu = 0.05.$			
Temp.	No. of readings taken with diff. conc. of reactants.	Instability constant.	$\Delta F (= RT \ln K)$ (in kcal.).
20.0°	8	$(2.34 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-4}$	(4.86 ± 0.25)
28.5°	10	(2.02 ± 0.07)	(5.10 ± 0.33)
40.0°	9	(1.59 ± 0.11)	(5.44 ± 0.24)

From the slope of the curve, obtained on plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 2), ΔH of the reaction has been calculated to be (-3.66 ± 0.14) kcal. Assuming this to be constant over the range of experimental temperature, ΔS of the reaction has also been calculated and is (29.1 ± 1.5) e.u.

The values of thermodynamic functions indicate that the stability of the chelate is mainly due to the entropy increase, similar to our observations on chelates of Al^{3+} ions and Fe^{3+} ions².

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